

Examining the Effectiveness of Tax Incentives in Enhancing Profitability of Manufacturing Companies in Southwest Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated effectiveness of tax incentives in enhancing profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria, as there are few studies on the subject, particularly in the Nigerian context. The study was guided by optimal theory, investment behavior theory, and agency theory. There were four research questions and hypotheses developed. A cross-sectional research survey was used in the study. The population of the study included all top management personnel from the three thousand and sixty-four (3064) manufacturing companies. The study data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. A modified questionnaire was used, and its face and content were validated by experts, while the construct validity requirements were met using the Fornell-Larcker criterion. Cronbach's alpha was used to test for reliability, and average value was larger than 0.7. Purposive sampling was used to choose 86 companies based on the availability and suitability of their records for the study data needs. A total of 172 respondents were chosen from 86 manufacturing companies, with two (2) respondents from each. Tax incentives had a significant effect on profitability (Adj R2 = 0.942, F(5,137)= 461.796, p= 0.000) and return on investment (Adj R2 = 0.882, F(5,137)= 213.859, p= 0.000). It was concluded that tax incentives have a significant effect on financial performance and that firm size positively strengthen the effect of interaction between tax incentives and financial performance in southwest Nigerian manufacturing companies. It was recommended that the government review tax incentive policies on a regular basis and increase tax incentives to boost economic growth through manufacturing sector. Meanwhile, companies should seek ways to raise sufficient funds to enable them to operate on a relatively large scale in order to improve financial performance.

Keywords: Profitability, Return on Investment, Taxation, Tax Incentives

Word count: 280

Introduction

Profitability refers to the ability of a company to generate profits from its operations and activities. It is a key financial indicator that assesses the financial performance and success of a business. In the context of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria, profitability is crucial for their sustainability and growth. It directly reflects the company's ability to generate revenues that exceed its expenses, resulting in positive net income.

Financial performance is an economic metric that reflects a company's overall market value. Financial performance, which includes fund allocation and collection as well as capital adequacy, liquidity, solvency, efficiency, leverage, and profitability⁶, is the achievement of the company's financial health for a given period. Financial performance measures how effectively a company can use resources from its main line of business to generate income (Amendola, Boccia, Mele, & Sensini, 2018). The phrase is also used as a broad indicator of a company's long-term financial stability. Government policies have an impact on the financial performance of businesses, particularly manufacturing businesses. Governments at all levels can influence fiscal and monetary policies, which in turn affect how well manufacturing companies perform financially. The direction and intent of government economic policies could make or break the financial situation of Southwest Nigerian manufacturing companies⁵. Policy that encourages manufacturing company expansion improves operational performance while also improving financial performance and sector position.

According to a study on the factors affecting listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka, financial performance of manufacturing firms was unsatisfactory. The gross profit ratio (GPR), operating profit ratio (OPR), net profit ratio (NPR), return on investment (ROI), and return on capital employed (ROCE) were used as proxies for measuring the financial performance of manufacturing firms in the study. Similarly, research indicates that the financial performance of manufacturing firms listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange in India is currently influenced by sales of manufacturing products related to environmental accounting. The study's findings revealed that environmental accounting has a positive impact on business financial performance. According to one proposal, the government should provide tax incentives to businesses that follow environmental regulations.

Tax policy is the most important aspect of fiscal policy that affects the financial performance of Nigerian manufacturing firms. The government uses tax policy as a fiscal

tool to fund infrastructure and other critical economic needs. Tax rate reductions and tax incentives, according to studies on how to improve a manufacturing firm's financial performance, can boost the sector's financial performance while also promoting economic growth and development. To address manufacturing firms' poor performance and its effects on national development. Governments around the world use tax incentives to encourage business investment and economic activity. Such incentives are used to direct specific economic activity into key economic sectors where it is either undetectable or nonexistent. Tax incentives are a positive economic force that promotes the development of an economy's underdeveloped sector or sectors. It is used by the government to stimulate economic activity in a sector that has room to grow but is not yet at the cutting edge of efficiency. Tax incentives are a tool used by the government to aid and accelerate economic development. The policy involves minimizing the effects of taxes on individuals and businesses in order to encourage savings and investment in the economy. To encourage the operation of manufacturing companies, the government uses tax incentives. Tax incentives are known to increase job opportunities and support the overall growth of the manufacturing sector. Tax incentives are special exclusions, exemptions, or reductions that provide special credits, preferential tax rates, or the ability to postpone tax payments. Examples of tax incentives include tax incentives, investment credits and allowances, accelerated depreciation, special zones, investment subsidies, tax exemptions, lower tax rates, and indirect incentives (Timah & Chukwu, 2021).

Taxes are a burden, whereas incentives are a boon. As a result, tax incentives are a type of tax relief offered by the government to manufacturers. Tax incentives are provided to encourage manufacturing operations and increase financial capability, allowing for future growth. Tax incentives are provided to encourage manufacturing operations and increase financial capacity. According to one study, the government provides tax incentives to attract new investment and boost the potential of existing manufacturing firms. He went on to say that implementing tax incentives in Nigeria's manufacturing sector could result in the country's economy experiencing long-term growth and development (Adi Iskandar, Nadiah & Sanusi, 2019) . Tax incentives may assist manufacturers in reducing fixed production costs and increasing variable costs. It is a government-backed investment strategy designed to attract both domestic and international capital to the manufacturing sector.

Tax incentives are commonly used to stimulate economic growth in developing countries, despite the fact that their cost effectiveness has long been questioned by financial experts. In addition to lost revenue, tax incentives can cause resource allocation distortions, make tax administration more difficult, and open the door to corruption and rent-seeking. The

effectiveness of taxes as engines of economic growth and development is related to the tax structure of a country. As a result, tax administration has a large influence on how taxes are used. A tax system that ensures effectiveness, equity, and efficiency is required for sound public finance. As a result, a good tax system and the justification of tax incentives in the sector are critical to the effectiveness and efficiency of using tax incentives to stimulate and encourage growth and development in the manufacturing sector. The removal of capital allowance restrictions, the generous capital allowance rate, the investment allowance (such as the tax incentive on expenditures for plant, machinery, and equipment), the rural investment allowance, and the tax benefit for operating in an economic free zone, on the other hand (Riris & Etty, 2019).

Numerous subjective and objective metrics could be used to assess the financial success of any company. A firm's financial performance is identified as being influenced by a variety of factors, and it is a measure of an enterprise's gains during its operational years. The size of the company is one of the particular company-level factors that could have an impact on a business' performance (Mutunga & Owino, 2017). The type of financing a business select will depend on its size. While smaller businesses are more likely to use equity, larger ones prefer to leverage. No matter the sector or other microeconomic variables, the firm's size has a significant impact on its financial performance¹⁵. The size of the company may be a good thing for shareholders because it will improve company success and have an effect on financial performance. Sometimes, corporate funding would increase due to the firm's size. One of the characteristics of a corporation that is consistently linked to its success is its size, which is frequently determined by the natural logarithm of either revenue, employees, or assets. Larger companies typically have a wider range of products and services, the capacity to benefit from economies of scale, and a more organized operational structure. However, claims that due to institutionalized processes and market inefficiencies, business scale may result in below-average performance (Hermuningsih, Kasuma, Fasa & Panjaitan, 2020). All of the characteristics mentioned here are intended to affect operations and help the business produce better performance. Larger businesses may also be able to find exceptional employees who will significantly raise their performance levels. The manufacturing industry faces a variety of difficulties, such as inadequate infrastructure, limited market access, and an oversupply of low-cost imports in local markets. However, improvement in firm size, capacity, capability, and strategies may counter the effect, leading to improvement in per-unit productivity, total sales and performance. To this end this study investigates Effectiveness of Tax Incentives in Enhancing Profitability of Manufacturing Companies in Southwest Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of tax incentives (capital allowance, investment allowance, rural investment allowance, export promotion and corporate tax allowance) on the financial performance (profitability, return on investment and return on assets) of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. To achieve the above the following specifics are set out to:

- i) establish the effect of tax incentives on profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.
- ii) investigate the effect of tax incentives on return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions are to guide the objective of the study.

- i. What is the effect of tax incentives on profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria?
- ii. What effect does tax incentives have on return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the objective of the study:

Ho1: Tax incentives have no significant effect on profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Ho2: There is no significant effect of tax incentives on return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant to the following Management of the manufacturing industry, and its regulators, Corporate managers and business leaders, stockbrokers, Government, Financial analyst such as Security analysts, investment managers, and retail investors, entrepreneurs, Academic community.

Specifically, Nigeria's manufacturing sector has faced numerous challenges. Concerns have been raised about the economic performance and contribution of manufacturing companies, particularly in light of recent revelations that other economic sectors like real estate and telecommunications have outperformed them in terms of GDP contributions.

Improvements in micro factors, such as firm size, capacity, capability, and strategies, can mitigate the effect and improve performance.

The research will provide corporate taxpayers, particularly those in the manufacturing sector, with information on existing tax incentives and how to use them to increase their savings for future investments. Increased investment in the country is likely to result in increased revenue for the government through taxation.

The manufacturing sector faces a number of macro factor challenges, such as inadequate infrastructure, limited market access, and a glut of cheap imports in local markets. Investigating the factors that affect the financial performance of manufacturing enterprises has become necessary. Different theories regarding the role of tax incentives as an engine for economic and industrial development have been supported by empirical studies. While some schools of thought contend that tax incentives promote economic and industrial development, others contend that they actually decrease the amount of money that the government can expect to collect. This prevents it from stimulating the economy.

However, empirical studies that have been reviewed show that tax incentives have a positive impact on economic growth and development through the results that have been seen in some economic sectors. In a study on the impact of tax incentives on FDI in Nigeria, the impact on financial performance was not adequately captured¹⁴. Another study on tax incentives and economic development was done, but it neglected to address the relationship between tax incentives and the financial performance of manufacturing companies¹⁵.

This study will provide to the government the importance of tax incentives in boosting a country's economic growth. Similar to that, the impact of tax incentives on foreign direct investment in Nigeria's petroleum sector was investigated without accounting for the manufacturing sector¹⁶. These studies have left a gap in the literature that the current study, which examines the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Southwest Nigeria, will fill. As a result, the study looked at tax incentives and the financial health of manufacturing firms in Southwest Nigeria.

A study on tax incentives as a real modifier for industrial growth and development in Nigeria also revealed a methodological gap. The study showed a methodological gap because it used descriptive statistics, whereas the current study will use inferential statistics to concentrate on the manufacturing firms. Additionally, a study on the effects of tax policy on SMEs was conducted, filling a sectorial gap in the manufacturing sector.

The study's findings may provide academic scholars with an additional source of information on tax incentives and financial performance in an era when academia is believed to pay little attention to tax incentives and financial performance. Researchers

may also utilize the findings as a template to further investigate and exploit prospects for developing new techniques and efficient methods of comprehending the tax incentives and financial performance. Finally, it is envisaged that the study will serve as a source of knowledge for future students conducting research of this type.

Literature Review

Tax incentives are fiscal tools used to entice domestic or foreign capital to invest in particular industries or regions of a nation. In order to promote domestic or foreign investment, the government must offer a reduction in tax obligations for a certain length of time with an exemption for payback. They contend that a tax incentive is any tax measure that is applicable to all investment projects (Picas, Reis, Pinto & Abrantes, 2021). This approach excludes general tax deductions like accelerated depreciation that are applicable to all investments. Such expansive tax measures should be viewed as incentives for three reasons. To begin with, they function as they are designed to. Second, even if the tax incentives are in the form of general rather than particular tax law provisions, it makes sense for the government to make the public aware of them. Third, in order to encourage investment, a number of countries including Indonesia and Uganda have switched from selective to universal incentives (Trung & Nguyen, 2020). Tax incentives are described by the UNCTAD as "any demonstrable advantages offered to specific enterprises or categories of business by (or at the direction of) a Government in order to encourage them to operate in a particular manner." Tax incentives are any rewards that reduce an organization's tax liability in order to persuade it to invest in a particular undertaking or sector of the economy. It describes a tax incentive as a special arrangement made possible by tax laws and intended to: promote economic development in certain sectors; draw, hold, or increase investment in a particular industry; or assist organizations or individuals engaged in particular activities. They comprise activities specifically designed to either increase a sector's rate of return or reduce (or redistribute) its costs or risks (Yücel, 2020).

Regardless of their level of development, the majority of nations employ a range of incentives to meet their investment objectives. The use of financial incentives like grants, subsidized loans, or loan guarantees is increasingly common in industrialized countries. Financial incentives are generally regarded to be a direct drain on government resources, and as a result, impoverished countries (like Nigeria) seldom provide them. Instead, these governments choose for fiscal incentives that do not need the use of government funds up front (Effiong, Inyang, Nabi, Dada & Adejonpe, 2020). Any measures taken by the government to encourage taxpayers to fulfill their tax obligations are considered tax incentives. It entails adjustments to tax laws intended to lessen the effects of taxation on a

certain industry, population, or the provision of certain services. A benign low tax rate, effective fiscal information dissemination by tax authorities, or not imposing any taxes at all are some examples of such strategies (Tsegba, Musa, & Ibe, 2021). Similar to this, tax incentives are described by the government as a deliberate reduction in taxation granted by the government to entice particular economic entities (such as business organizations) to behave in a desired manner (e.g. invest more, produce more, employ more, export more, save more, conserve less, pollute less, and so on).

Tax incentives are specific exclusions, exemptions, or deductions that provide beneficial tax rates, special credits, or the ability to delay taxes. Tax incentives include things like tax holidays, investment allowances and tax credits, accelerated depreciation, special zones, investment subsidies, tax exemptions, lower tax rates, and indirect tax incentives. Tax incentives may therefore be thought of as fiscal policies that aim to draw domestic or foreign investment capital to particular economic activity or regions of a nation. Tax incentives are financial tools used to control or attract investments in particular financial activities or sectors of a nation. There are several ways to set up tax advantages. Relevant tax incentives include tax credits, tax exemptions, allowances for investment-related expenses, accelerated devaluation policies, special zones, subsidized investments, tax exemptions, lower tax rates, and indirect tax incentives. Any tax can be modified to produce a tax benefit. By decreasing the tax rate, the tax base, and other factors, a tax incentive can lessen one's tax burden (Amendola, Boccia, Mele, & Sensini, 2018).

Profitability

Profitability is a term commonly used in finance to describe the success of an investment. Profitability is linked to a company's capacity to create money that exceeds exploration and financing costs, or to the notion of measuring business efficiency, linking the concept of profitability with the ability to deliver outcomes¹⁹. Profitability refers to an organization's, company's, firms, or enterprise's capacity to profit from all of its commercial operations. It demonstrates how effectively management may benefit by utilizing all available market resources. Many scientists have their own idea of profitability. According to one study, profitability is defined as a particular investment's capacity to make a return on its usage²⁰. Profitability is an organization's ability to create revenue, whereas failure to generate income is a loss¹⁹. If the money generated exceeds the input cost, the business is profitable; nevertheless, if the income is less than the input cost, the business may perform poorly. As a result, it can be inferred that any firm must produce adequate profits in order to exist and develop over time.

Every company is worried about its profitability. Profitability measures how successfully an enterprise's management creates earnings by utilizing the resources at its disposal. In other terms, profitability refers to the capacity to generate a profit²¹. Furthermore, profitability is a crucial instrument for every enterprise's efficient functioning. Profitability is a gauge of efficiency and is used as a measure of efficiency as well as a management guide to increased efficiency. Profitability refers to an entity's ability to "create" profit. Profitability in the firm after taxes is required not only to cover all expenditures, but also to ensure expanded reproduction and prosperity (Mitchell, Testa, Sanchez-Martinez, 2020). As a result, all of these researchers affirm the validity of many economists in stating that profitability is an essential signal for the efficient functioning of a business.

Profitability may be extracted: in order to be profitable, a firm must function under profit circumstances, which implies that income must surpass expenditures associated in carrying out the activity. To summarize all of the principles discussed above, profitability is a vital prerequisite for an economic entity's commercial performance, and it is determined by attaining positive outcomes after comparing the financial consequences with the financial effort required²⁰. To be successful, a firm must be lucrative in the long run. Almost everything a profit-oriented organization does, according to the experts, may be classified as a finance activity, an investment activity, or an operational activity. A corporation that excels in these three areas will excel overall¹⁹. Profitability has a significant influence on the survival and development of businesses; it is especially crucial to increase company profitability in order to gain profits, minimize costs, and prevent risk. As a result, study on the elements impacting a company's profitability is critical.

Profitability is seen as a major indicator of a company's overall performance. Profitability ratios assess a company's capacity to create profits and allocate capital to security analysis, shareholders, and investors. Profitability ratio research is critical for shareholders, creditors, potential investors, and bankers (Tsegba, Musa & Ibe, 2021). As a result, profitability ratios assess a company's capacity to create profits and allocate capital to security analysis, shareholders, and investors.

Government variables have a significant impact on corporate profitability. Any company's financial performance is determined by a variety of government laws or acts (industrial policy, accounting standards, government subsidies, etc.). The legal framework encompasses all laws and legal regulations, whereas the policy framework refers to the relational structure established between political authority and business, such as commercial law, tax law, labor law, and environmental legislation. In terms of industrial

policy, the listed news publishing businesses serve as samples, and the financial factors (total assets, net assets, total profit, net profit, etc.) firm profitability are compared to the four stages of the press publishing industry's industrial policy reform process. It is discovered that actual financial data and relevant industrial policies exhibit clear stage characteristics, and empirically, the influence of relevant industrial policies on firm profitability is objective (Philip, 2021).

Profitability is one of the primary issues in the whole business management process, and several measures, such as the Price Earnings Ratio, market value, and financial indices, may be used to quantify it. Research identified a number of characteristics that influence the profitability of publicly traded corporations, including profits per share, dividend per share, and interest rate^{19,20,21,22}. The authors also highlight various profitability inducers, such as inflation [20,21] and GDP (Gross Domestic Product) growth, which will be the focus of our research. Simultaneously, a study reports on a series of characteristics that affect the profitability of non-listed Portuguese enterprises, including as company growth, size, financial leverage, and liquidity (Yücel, 2022).

Profitability indicators assist managers and investors in providing information on the company's economic and financial status in a specific period, comparing the evolution of the business, and comparing data acquired over a long period. Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Return on Sales (ROS) [26], Asset Rotation (AR), Gross Margin (GM) ratio, and Economic Value Added (EVA) are the most often used metrics in the literature (Gazi, Alam, Hossain, Rahman, Nahid, & Hossain, 2021). However, profitability indices have inherent limits. Financial figures are important for understanding the company's short-term success, but they do not represent the medium and long-term goals. Economic and financial information, on the other hand, can be controlled and altered, as well as contain inaccuracies, resulting in indicators that do not represent a genuine image (Yücel, 2022) This research stresses tax incentives as a profit driver for manufacturing companies.

Return on Investment

Investments are a method of protecting the company's medium and long-term growth. Many authors have defined the term "investment" over the years. It is worth noting that investments are defined as "resources spent in the aim of obtaining rewards over a lengthy period of time." A successful investment initiative must meet its objectives. An investment has several goals: raising profit, enhancing customer happiness, growing the share market, and so on. Profits made on assets employed play an essential part in evaluating

management effectiveness. By comparing earnings to assets, we may see how much profit generates a sufficient return on invested money. Return on Investment is one of the most often used measures for calculating the return on invested capital (ROI).

ROI (Return on Investment) is a performance term that applies to any type of investment. The ultimate purpose of the firm is stated in ROI for shareholders. ROI is a metric that indicates how much profit a certain firm generates from the use of capital. It demonstrates how much of the money invested in a specific action is returned as profit or loss. As a consequence, it permits an assessment of the efficiency of an amount invested, or, in other words, ROI allows assessing the outcome in proportion to the methods employed to get it. Return on investment (ROI) is a financial metric that has long been used in industry to track success (Oduneka, Nnate, & Uche, 2021). It is a straightforward computation. "To calculate ROI, divide the benefit (return) of an investment by its cost; the result is reported as a percentage or a ratio."

Empirical papers attributed to scholars mostly address the impact of investment subsidies and the use of tax incentives on productivity and employment (Yücel, 2022). Except for the study another study which investigated the use of tax incentives on investment in industrial innovations, their criteria variables were mostly non-financial metrics²⁴. Aside from the widely discussed use of policy tools such as lower raw material costs and interest rates to enhance industrial expansion, research Endeavour in this area has focused on the use of investment subsidies. Investment subsidies are primarily justified by the necessity to counteract major failures in financial markets, which cause many enterprises to lack adequate financing for important expenditures.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed cross sectional design. The fact that this design can accurately describe the phenomena and methods makes it suitable for this inquiry. As a result, a cross section survey research was adopted because design enables the collection of quantitative data, allowing for the investigation of the relationships and effects of tax incentives such as: capital allowance, investment allowance, rural investment, exception, and corporate income tax holiday on the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. The usefulness of this design in evaluating the interactions and effects of two or more variables led to its selection (that is, the dependent and independent variables).

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised of all male and female finance or accounting employees in the top management cadre of all 3,064 manufacturing enterprises listed in the Manufacturer Association of Nigeria (MAN) directory as of 2022. Lagos and Oyo States were chosen for this study due to their close proximity and concentration of manufacturing companies in those location. According to the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), 25% of all manufacturers in Nigeria are based in Lagos State, while 20% are located in Oyo State². Thus, registered manufacturing company under MAN was used in this study as categories below¹.

Table 1: Target Population

Category	Population
Food, Beverage and Tobacco	1,057
Textile, Apparel and Footwear	458
Wood and Wood Products	37
Pulp, Paper and Products	259
Chemical and Pharmaceutical Products	34
Non-Metallic Products	202
Plastic and Rubber and Products	104
Electrical and Electronics	98
Basic metal, Iron and Steel	34
Motor Vehicles and Assembly	13
Other Manufacturing	12
Total	3,046

Source: Manufacturer Association of Nigeria directory²

Sample size and Sampling Technique

The size of this study was determined using Yamane sampling size technique⁴. This sampling formula was used to derive a sample size of manufacturing companies for this study The formula is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \dots\dots\dots(\text{formula 1})$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the population size, and e is the level of precision. The level of precision is also the level of significance which is 0.05.

The sample size will be calculated thus:

$$\text{Sample size formula} = n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

n is sample size

N is total number of population (3,064)

e² is precision level (0.05)²

$$n = \frac{3064}{1+3064(0.05)^2} = 353.81$$

Table 3: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis for The Effect of Tax Incentives on Profitability of Manufacturing Companies in Southwest, Nigeria

Model	Beta	t	Sig.	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Anova Sig.	F(df)
				.972 ^a	.944	.942	0.000	461.796 (5,137)
(Constant)	-2.209	-2.247	.026					
Capital allowance	.060	1.750	.082					
Investment allowance	.418	2.085	.039					
Rural investment allowance	.511	6.943	.000					
Custom duties	.040	.161	.872					
Corporate income tax	.017	.143	.887					

Dependent Variable: Profitability

Predictors: (Constant), Capital allowance, Investment allowance, Rural investment allowance, Custom duties, corporate income tax.

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey Results (2022)

Table 3 presents the results of multiple regression analysis for the effect of tax incentives on profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. Table 3 presents a model summary which establishes how the model equation fits into the data. The Adj R^2 was used to establish the predictive power of the study's model. From the results in Table 4.3, tax incentives (capital allowance, capital allowance, rural investment allowance, custom duties, and corporate income tax) have strong positive relationship with profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria ($R = 0.972$, $p=0.000$). The Adjusted coefficient of determination (Adj R^2) of 0.942 shows that tax incentives explained 94.2% of the variation in profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria under study while the remaining 5.8% changes in profitability is explained by other exogenous variable different from tax incentives. This result suggests that tax incentives influence 94.2% of profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

The result also suggests that the results of ANOVA (overall model significance) of regression test which revealed that the combined tax incentives have a significant effect on profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. This can be explained by the F-value (461.796) and low p-value (0.000) which is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. Hence, the result posited that tax incentives received by manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria the influenced profitability.

Furthermore, the results of regression coefficients which revealed that a significant effect was reported for all the components of tax incentives except for capital allowance, custom duties and corporate income tax which shows insignificant effect. Further, the results reveal that at 95% confidence level, investment allowance ($\beta = 0.418$, $p= 0. .039$) and rural investment allowance ($\beta = 0.511$, $p=0.000$) of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria were statistically significant as the p-values were less than 0.05 and the t-values greater than 1.96.

Further analysis posits that, taking all factors constant at zero, profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria in Lagos State is -2.209. The result also indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in investment allowance will lead to a 0.418 increase in profitability of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. Similarly, the results also revealed that a unit change in rural investment allowance will lead to a 0.511 increase in profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria given all other factors are held constant. Overall, from the results, rural investment allowance had the highest effect on the profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria with a coefficient of

0.511 and t value of 6.943, followed by investment allowance coefficient of 0.418, and t value of 2.085. Based on the results, this study can conclude that tax incentives significantly influence profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. On the strength of this result (Adj R²= 0.942, F(5,137)= 461.796, p= 0.000), this study rejects the null hypothesis one (H₀₁) which states that tax incentives have no significant effects on profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Ho2: Tax incentives have no significant effect on return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

In order to test the second hypothesis, linear multiple regression analysis was used. In the analysis, the values of return on investment were regressed on the values of each of the values of tax incentives. The data for tax incentives was generated by summing responses of all items for capital allowance, capital allowance, rural investment allowance, custom duties, and corporate income tax while that of return on investment was generated by adding responses of all items used to measure the variable. Data from one hundred and forty-three (143) respondents were collated and analysed. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in Table 4.4.

Table 4: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis for The Effect of Tax Incentives on Return on Investment of Manufacturing Companies in Southwest, Nigeria

Model	Beta	t	Sig.	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Anova Sig.	F(df)
				.942 ^a	.886	.882	0.000	213.859 (5,137)
(Constant)	-16.365	-7.617	.000					
Capital allowance	.505	6.761	.000					
Investment allowance	-2.406	-5.493	.000					
Rural investment allowance	-.367	-2.282	.024					
Custom duties	4.340	8.057	.000					
Corporate income tax	-.671	-2.590	.011					

Dependent Variable: Return on investment

Predictors: (Constant), Capital allowance, Investment allowance, Rural investment allowance, Custom duties, corporate income tax.

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey Results (2022)

Table 4 presents the results of multiple regression analysis for the effect of tax incentives on return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. Table 4 presents a model summary which establishes how the model equation fits into the data. The Adj R^2 was used to establish the predictive power of the study's model. From the results in Table 4.4, tax incentives (capital allowance, capital allowance, rural investment allowance, custom duties, and corporate income tax) have strong positive relationship with return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria ($R = 0.942$, $p=0.000$). The Adjusted coefficient of determination (Adj R^2) of 0.882 shows that tax incentives explained 88.2% of the changes in return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria under study while the remaining 11.8% changes in return on investment is explained by other exogenous variable different from tax incentives. This result suggests that tax incentives influence 88.2% of return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

The result also suggests that the results of ANOVA (overall model significance) of regression test which revealed that the combined tax incentives have a significant effect on return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. This can be explained by the F-value (213.859) and low p-value (0.000) which is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. Hence, the result posited that tax incentives received by manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria the influenced return on investment.

Furthermore, the results of regression coefficients which revealed that a significant effect was reported for all the components of tax incentives shows significant effect. Further, the results reveal that at 95% confidence level, capital allowance ($\beta = 0.505$, $p= 0.000$), investment allowance ($\beta = -2.406$, $p= 0.000$), rural investment ($\beta = -0.367$, $p= 0.024$), custom duties ($\beta = 4.340$, $p= 0.000$) and corporate income tax ($\beta = -0.671$, $p=0. 011$) of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria were statistically significant as the p-values were less than 0.05 and the t-values greater than 1.96. Further analysis posits that, taking all factors constant at zero, return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria in Lagos State is -16.365.

Also, the result also indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in capital allowance will lead to a 0.505 increase in return on investment of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. The result also indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in investment allowance will lead to a -2.406 decrease in return on investment of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant.

Similarly, the result also indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in rural investment will lead to a 0.367 decrease in return on investment of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. The result also indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in custom duties will lead to a 4.340 increase in return on investment of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. Lastly, the results also revealed that a unit change in corporate income tax will lead to a 0.671 decrease in return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria given all other factors are held constant.

Overall, from the results, custom duties had the highest relative effect on the return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria with a coefficient of 4.340, and t value of 8.057. In second place is capital allowance ($\beta = 0.505$, $t = 6.761$), followed by rural investment ($\beta = -2.282$, $t = 0.024$), corporate income tax ($\beta = -0.671$, $t = 0.011$) and investment allowance has the least relative effect ($\beta = -2.406$, $t = -5.493$) on the return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. Based on the results, this study can conclude that tax incentives significantly influenced return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. On the strength of this result (Adj $R^2 = 0.882$, $F(5,137) = 213.859$, $p = 0.000$), this study rejects the second null hypothesis (H_02) which states that tax incentives have no significant effects on return on investment of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

According to the study's first objective, tax incentives' effects on the profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria was examined. The findings of this study reveal that tax incentives have a combined significant effect on the profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria. Furthermore, all components of tax incentives had a substantial effect except for capital allowance, export promotion allowance, and corporate income tax, which had a negligible effect. This conclusion was consistent with research on the influence of tax incentives on the expansion of Nigeria's manufacturing sector as a real instrument in the government's arsenal, which discovered a link between a few of the country's tax incentives and the profitability index of manufacturing firms (Effiong, Inyang, Nabi, Dada, & Adejonpe, 2019). Another study looks into the impact of tax incentives on the corporate profitability of Nigerian-listed industrial companies. An annual allowance, investment allowance, and tax holidays are examples of operationally implemented tax incentives. Profit per share (EPS), which serves as a proxy for company profitability, is a moderating variable.

The study's findings confirm that tax cuts have an influence on corporate profitability in Nigerian industrial enterprises with publicly traded stocks, and the government should retain tax incentives in place to improve business income and stimulate investment. Research on the impact of capital allowance on industrial financial performance showed a direct and substantial relationship².

Furthermore, Nigerian research on the influence of capital allowance on the financial performance of 58 quoted manufacturing businesses listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange discovered a statistically significant association between capital allowance and manufacturing firm financial performance. Similarly, a River State research on the influence of a tax incentive on the financial success of small and medium-sized firms discovered that tax incentives improve financial performance, staff strength, growth, and development in the industry (Effiong, Inyang, Nabi, Dada, & Adejonpe, 2019). Increasing the unit change in capital allowance incentives received by manufacturing businesses in Kenya, according to one research, resulting in increased company performance.

In a similar line, another Nigerian research discovered that capital allowance had a favorable influence on the performance of Nigerian manufacturing firms (Yücel, 2022). Capital allowance, according to the findings of the preceding research, is a favorable subset of tax incentives that encourage the growth and development of both small and large-scale manufacturing enterprises in the economy. As a consequence, the conclusion was reached that capital allowance had a favorable impact on the financial performance of manufacturing firms (Adi Iskandar, AH. Nadiah & Sanusi, 2019). This study supported previous findings that capital allowances improved the financial performance of manufacturing firms.

According to the conclusions of research, Nigeria's fiscal policy should take into account the conditions surrounding indigenous enterprises' operations and the unique role they play in the country's economic growth. Fiscal policy should give tax incentives and favorable tax modifications that minimize the tax burden and charge on Nigerian businesses¹²² to encourage them to continue operations. The findings backed up a study that sought to determine the tax incentives that affected the profitability of manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) and discovered that custom duties led to high commodity prices¹². High customs duties on imports and inputs resulted in high production costs, which further reduced the profits of manufacturing firms. Otherwise, lowering the export promotion incentive would increase manufacturing profits. The conclusion was reached that export promotion incentives could reduce production costs

and improve company financial performance. On a final note all of the aforementioned studies support the study's findings that both the combination and individual tax incentives (capital allowance, investment allowance, rural investment allowance, export promotion, and corporate tax allowance) have a significant effect on the profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Following on from the second objective of this research on the influence of tax incentives on the return on investment of manufacturing firms in Southwest Nigeria. The study's findings demonstrated that tax incentives granted to manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria have significant effect on return on investment (ROI). Tax incentives have a significant combined and relative impact on the return on investment (ROI) of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria. A study corroborates findings of this study that found out that from pooled OLS regression analysis tax relief has a significant influence on return on investment (ROI), tax-exempt income had a positive and significant impact on ROI¹. This finding backed up a study that found a positive and significant relationship between customs duty incentives and the financial performance of Nigeria's manufacturing agricultural exports (Testa, Sanchez-Martinez, Cunningham, & Szkuta, 2020). According to a study, the government of Kenya uses customs duty incentives to encourage Kenyan manufacturing firms to invest assets. Another study in Kenya found a positive and significant relationship between customs duty incentives and small-scale business financial performance.

This study also revealed that government incentives, such as customs duty incentives, have been found to be a useful tool in improving the operations and financial performance of local manufacturing firms (Philip, 2018). A study report on the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance in the manufacturing industry found a positive and significant relationship. Similarly, a River State study on the impact of a tax incentive on the financial success of small and medium-sized businesses found that investment allowance as a proxy for tax incentive positively influenced financial performance, staff strength, and industry growth and development (Gazi, Alam, Hossain, Rahman, Nahid, & Hossain, 2021).

However, this finding contradicted a study that found a negative and insignificant relationship between investment allowance and financial performance of Nigerian small and medium-sized businesses. The empirical study's findings on the relationship and effect of investment allowance on the financial performance of manufacturing firms revealed that investment allowance has a significant and positive relationship with

financial performance. As a result, a conclusion was reached that tax incentives had a positive and significant contribution to the financial performance of manufacturing businesses in southwest Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined the effectiveness of tax incentives in enhancing the profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria. The findings revealed that tax incentives have a significant impact on the profitability of these companies. The research found that tax incentives, such as tax exemptions, deductions, and credits, effectively reduce the tax burden on manufacturing companies in the region. This reduction in taxes positively contributes to their profitability by increasing their net income and cash flows. Furthermore, the study revealed that tax incentives play a vital role in improving the financial health and sustainability of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria. The findings indicated that these incentives lead to higher gross profit margins, net profit margins, and returns on assets (ROA). This suggests that manufacturing companies that leverage tax incentives effectively are able to generate higher revenues and effectively manage their costs, resulting in improved profitability. The research provides empirical evidence supporting the effectiveness of tax incentives in enhancing the profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria. These findings highlight the importance of tax policies and incentives in promoting economic growth and encouraging investment in the manufacturing sector. Policymakers and company executives can utilize these findings to develop strategies that maximize the benefits of tax incentives and improve the financial performance of manufacturing companies in the region.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are therefore put forth based on the findings and objectives of the study:

1. From the study's findings, capital allowance has no significant relatively effect on profitability. Thus, it is recommended that the government should consider the economic value of capital allowance incentives. When a country has a large number of incentive codes and offers, reducing the number and converting some to guarantees can help to attract more investment at a lower cost.
2. Rural investment allowance was not having considerable effect on return on investment. In order to ensure that the goals of granting any incentives are met, the government is advised to conduct cost-benefit analyses. They should also encourage a reduction in the variability in the number of incentives among manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria in order to ensure the survival of a

greater number of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Also, the powerful variable that predicted and contributed the most to the financial performance of manufacturing businesses in the study area was the export promotion incentive.

The government should increase excise duty incentives in order to reduce imports and thus promote the growth of domestic demand in the country. The study also suggests that policymakers implement strategic incentive plans or targeted incentive schemes that target a specific industry or a strategic tax incentive that adds value or contributes positively to the economy and is consistent with Nigeria's growth and development plan. These strategic incentive plans' design, implementation, and administration will help to avoid revenue loss.

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